

ISic0671

I.Sicily inscription 0671

Language

Latin

Type

honorific

Material

stone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Tyndaris

Place of origin (modern)

Tindari

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Tindari, Area archeologica Teatro antico e Antiquarium di Tindari

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR081483

0. [---]

1. [Au]gus [to]

2. d (ecreto) d (ecurionum)

0. [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 175740

EDR 081483

EDCS 6100248

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1989.0338a

Manganaro, G. 1989. Iscrizioni Latine nuove e vecchie della Sicilia. *Epigraphica*. 51: 161-196. At 162 no.2 fig.2

Fasolo, M. 2013. Tyndaris e il suo territorio. Volume 1. Introduzione alla carta archeologica del territorio di Tindari. Rome. At 78 no.14 fig.43

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